

The historical evolution of European medical device regulation: from fragmented national systems to a harmonized supranational framework

Iana Simova^{1,2}

1 Expert Panel, European Medicines Agency, Amsterdam, Netherlands

2 Medical University Pleven, Pleven, Bulgaria

3 Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

4 Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Iana Simova (ianasimova@gmail.com)

Received 16 January 2026 ♦ Accepted 4 February 2026 ♦ Published 19 February 2026

Citation: Simova I, Petkova V, Ognyanov S, Andreevska K, Dimitrov M (2026) The historical evolution of European medical device regulation: from fragmented national systems to a harmonized supranational framework. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e185464>

Abstract

This review traces European medical device regulation from fragmented national systems to the harmonized framework established by Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR) and Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR). It examines the pre-harmonization period (1957–1985), characterized by diverse national approaches in Western and Eastern Europe, including Bulgaria’s regulatory development during the post-communist transition. It explores the New Approach to technical harmonization (1985), the directive era (1990–2000), and how regulatory crises—including the Guidant pacemaker failures, the DePuy ASR hip prosthesis scandal, and the PIP breast implant fraud—served as stress tests confirming the necessity of reforms. Special attention is given to emerging challenges from artificial intelligence in medical devices following the adoption of the AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689).

Keywords

AI Act, Bulgaria, CE marking, clinical evaluation, MDR, medical device regulation

Introduction

The regulation of medical devices in Europe is among the more complex areas of health policy, directly affecting patient safety, technological innovation, and market access for products ranging from simple bandages and tongue depressors to implantable cardiac devices, complex imaging systems, and AI-powered diagnostic software. Unlike pharmaceuticals, which act through pharmacological, im-

munological, or metabolic means, medical devices achieve their intended purpose through physical, mechanical, or other non-pharmacological mechanisms, presenting regulatory challenges that require frameworks distinct from those governing medicinal products (EUR-Lex 2017a).

The Treaty of Rome, signed on 25 March 1957, established the legal foundations for future harmonization of medical device regulations through Article 100, which granted the Council powers to adopt directives

for “the approximation of such laws, regulations, or administrative provisions of the Member States as directly affect the establishment or functioning of the common market” (EUR-Lex 1957) (Table 1). Article 235 further allowed the Community to take action in areas not explicitly provided for when necessary for Community objectives. However, the first two decades following the treaty were characterized by institutional passivity in the field of medical devices, with health considerations perceived as exclusive national prerogatives and the Community focusing primarily on industrial and agricultural harmonization.

Device diversity—encompassing more than 500,000 different products from tongue depressors to artificial hearts—necessitated the development of a classification-based approach that could accommodate different levels of risk while maintaining a coherent regulatory framework. Such challenges were compounded by rapid technological innovation, growing device complexity, increasing globalization of manufacturing and supply chains, and the emergence of novel product categories that blur traditional boundaries between devices, pharmaceuticals, and digital technologies.

The recent emergence of artificial intelligence in medical devices adds another layer of regulatory complexity that the European legislator has addressed through the AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689). It marks a shift in European regulatory philosophy, extending the traditional focus on physical safety to encompass algorithmic accountability, data governance, and the risks posed by machine learning systems in healthcare contexts.

This review traces the historical evolution of European medical device regulation from the fragmented national systems of the pre-harmonization era through the establishment of a supranational framework. It examines key regulatory models developed by Member States in both Western and Eastern Europe, with particular attention to the challenges faced by post-communist countries during their transition and EU accession. It explores the New Approach to technical harmonization, the directive era of the 1990s, regulatory crises that served as stress tests for the system, the reforms introduced by MDR and IVDR, and emerging challenges from AI-based devices.

The pre-harmonization era (1957–1985)

Early regulatory catalysts

The thalidomide tragedy (1957–1962) established principles influencing medical device oversight. The catastrophe, which caused severe congenital malformations in more than 10,000 children worldwide, led to Directive 65/65/EEC (26 January 1965), requiring evidence of safety and efficacy before market placement (EUR-Lex 1965; Daemmrich 2002). While focused on pharmaceuticals, it established precedents, including

pre-market assessment, mandatory adverse event reporting, and regulatory agencies with enforcement powers (Rägo and Santos 2008).

Western European national regulatory models

During 1960–1985, individual EEC states created independent regulatory frameworks reflecting their socio-cultural characteristics, creating trade barriers while providing varying levels of patient protection.

United Kingdom

Britain adopted a liberal regulatory model based on self-regulation, industry responsibility, and post-market surveillance rather than extensive pre-market control. Unlike continental European states that favored centralized prior approval systems, the United Kingdom avoided creating a system for pre-market device evaluation, instead relying on manufacturers' responsibility for product safety combined with systematic monitoring after devices reached the market.

Parliament's Medicines Act of 1968 provided the primary legislative framework for therapeutic products, but its scope regarding medical devices was extremely limited, explicitly including only products at the boundary between medicines and devices: anesthetic gases, resorbable surgical sutures, intrauterine contraceptive devices, and contact lenses with their solutions (Medicines Act 1968). Most medical devices fell outside this framework and were regulated primarily through general product safety legislation and voluntary industry standards.

In 1969, the Ministry of Health created the Scientific and Technical Board (STB)—an interdepartmental body responsible for the technical evaluation of medical equipment. The STB introduced the Manufacturers' Registration Scheme (MRS)—a voluntary scheme for manufacturer registration requiring compliance with good manufacturing practices and technical standards. Although formally voluntary, participation in the MRS quickly became *de facto* mandatory for companies wishing to supply the National Health Service (NHS), as hospitals increasingly required MRS registration as a condition for procurement.

Britain introduced an innovative system for the systematic reporting of incidents involving medical devices that would later influence European approaches. From 1970, the NHS introduced the requirement that all serious malfunctions be reported to central authorities within 24 hours. In 1978, a national pacemaker registry was established to track the long-term performance of these critical devices, followed by a heart valve registry in 1986. These registries, among the first of their kind in Europe, proved invaluable for identifying safety signals that only became apparent years after implantation. This emphasis on post-market monitoring and the principle of manufacturer responsibility became foundational elements of the future European system.

France

France was characterized by centralized prior control, strict approval procedures, and strong state intervention in health product markets—reflecting the traditional French approach to health regulation, in which the state assumes primary responsibility for protecting public health through ex ante controls (Hancher 1990). Its pharmaceutical tradition of strict regulation, dating back to the 19th century, exerted a strong influence on the approach to medical devices, leading to the development of pre-market assessment procedures that would later influence the European model.

Central to the French system was the “homologation” procedure—mandatory prior approval for certain high-risk devices administered by the Ministry of Health through the specialized agency Agence du Médicament. Homologation required the submission of an extensive dossier, including detailed technical specifications, production documentation, results of physico-chemical and biological tests, clinical data on efficacy and safety, and information on conditions of use and contraindications (Décret 1978). This approach anticipated many elements that would later appear in the European medical device directives.

France introduced another key element of the future European system—the network of accredited testing laboratories that performed technical evaluations on behalf of regulatory authorities. These French accredited laboratories—predecessors of notified bodies—developed technical expertise in areas such as biomaterials testing, electromedical equipment safety, and sterilization validation. The model demonstrated how strict regulatory control could be achieved without requiring the state to maintain all technical expertise internally—the Ministry of Health set general requirements and approved final decisions, while detailed technical evaluation was performed by specialized external experts. The principle of delegated technical evaluation became foundational for the European notified body system.

Germany

Germany’s regulatory environment was marked by institutional fragmentation between two parallel regimes—pharmaceutical legislation and technical regulation. Such dualism reflected deeper tensions in German regulatory philosophy between the health-oriented approach of pharmaceutical authorities, which focused on therapeutic efficacy and safety, and the safety-oriented approach of technical inspection bodies, which emphasized product conformity with engineering standards and protection against mechanical and electrical hazards.

Germany’s *Arzneimittelgesetz* (Pharmaceutical Law) of 1976 introduced the concept of “Scheinarzneimittel” or “fictitious drugs”—a German category including medical devices acting primarily through physical, mechanical, or chemical (non-pharmacological) means but used with therapeutic purposes similar to drugs. The legal construction allowed certain borderline products to be

regulated under pharmaceutical rules but left most medical devices outside the pharmaceutical framework.

Parallel to pharmaceutical regulation, Germany developed specialized technical legislation for medical equipment. The MedGV (*Medizinische-Geräteverordnung*) of 14 January 1985 extended the scope of general technical safety legislation to include electromedical and radiological devices (MedGV 1985). The ordinance introduced detailed technical requirements based on German and international standards, establishing a precedent for the standards-based approach that would later characterize European harmonization.

TÜV organizations (*Technischer Überwachungsverein*), with a long tradition in industrial safety since the late 19th century, adapted their procedures for medical applications during the 1960s (*Gerätesicherheitsgesetz* 1968). TÜV laboratories developed expertise in areas such as electrical safety of medical equipment, radiation protection in imaging systems, biocompatibility of implant materials, and validation of sterilization processes. The model of outsourcing technical expertise to accredited private organizations created a precedent that directly influenced the later European concept of “notified bodies.” The German approach also introduced systematic use of harmonized technical standards as an instrument for demonstrating conformity—this philosophy of “regulation through standardization” became central to the European New Approach of 1985.

Other Western European countries

Italy pioneered medical device legislation (*Regio Decreto* 1934) but faced contradiction between formal centralization and regional fragmentation under the Constitution of 1948 (*Costituzione Italiana* 1948). Italy’s Ministry of Health introduced mandatory registration in 1979 (*Ministero della Salute* 1979), yet twenty autonomous regions created fragmented evaluation requirements.

Spain’s Catalonia region created the *Agència d’Avaluació de Tecnologia i Recerca Mèdiques* (AATRM) in 1994, and it was one of Europe’s first Health Technology Assessment agencies, evaluating clinical benefit, economic feasibility, and health system impact, anticipating contemporary discussions about clinical effectiveness (Sampietro-Colom 2009). Scandinavian countries developed pragmatic systems with regional cooperation through the Nordic Council on Medicines (1975), demonstrating the feasibility of regulatory harmonization (Socialstyrelsen 1968; Nordic Council 1975).

Eastern Europe: from central planning to EU accession

After the fall of the Berlin Wall (1989), Eastern European countries faced major challenges—creating modern regulatory systems while dealing with economic crises and limited institutional capacity. Under the Semashko system, medical devices were treated as elements of planned production, with standards focusing on technical specifications rather than clinical safety.

Czechoslovakia acted quickly after the Velvet Revolution, aligning with European standards to demonstrate “returning to Europe.” By the mid-1990s, the Czech Republic had begun transposing European directives even before formal EU accession negotiations. Poland remained in a regulatory vacuum throughout the 1990s, introducing frameworks only during preparation for EU membership.

Bulgaria

Bulgaria experienced a difficult transition during the 1990s that created specific challenges for building regulatory capacity. Economic collapse was catastrophic—hyperinflation exceeded 1000% in 1997, the banking system failed completely, and massive emigration depleted the healthcare workforce of doctors, nurses, and technical specialists. The health system collapsed, with hospitals lacking even basic medications and supplies during the worst of the crisis.

Only after 1997, when the economy began to stabilize with the introduction of a currency board regime and World Bank structural adjustment support, did serious health reforms begin. Preparation for EU accession imposed accelerated harmonization requirements that tested the limits of Bulgaria’s nascent regulatory institutions (EUR-Lex 2005). Between 2003 and 2006, Bulgaria had to transpose the entire *acquis communautaire* in the field of medical devices—legislation that had taken Western European countries decades to develop (EUR-Lex 2006). During this critical period, the Bulgarian Drug Agency under Director Dr. Emil Hristov (2004–2009) led the separation of medical device regulation from pharmaceutical legislation and established Bulgaria’s participation in European Commission working groups on medical devices, including the Advisory Committee on the approximation of laws related to medical devices in Member States.

On 12 June 2007, six months after Bulgaria’s entry into the EU, the Law on Medical Devices (Bulgarian Law on Medical Devices 2007) entered into force, transposing Directives 93/42/EEC, 90/385/EEC, and 98/79/EC and creating a legal framework for regulating medical devices in accordance with European standards (Bulgarian Law on Medical Devices 2007). It designated the Bulgarian Drug Agency (BDA) as the competent authority for medical devices. The BDA assumed responsibility for registration of manufacturers and devices, designation and supervision of notified bodies, incident management and vigilance, and coordination of post-market surveillance activities across the Bulgarian market.

The initial implementation of the law encountered multiple significant challenges: registering thousands of devices already on the market had to be carried out within short deadlines; notified bodies had to be designated and accredited according to European standards; post-market surveillance systems had to be built from scratch with limited resources and expertise; and medical facilities had to adapt to new requirements for device tracking and incident reporting. The Bulgarian experience illustrates the

particular difficulties faced by countries that had to simultaneously build regulatory capacity and transpose complex European legislation without the decades of gradual institutional development that Western European countries had enjoyed. These challenges continue to influence Bulgaria’s regulatory capacity under the more demanding requirements of MDR.

The New Approach and directive era (1985–2000)

The 1985 regulatory shift

By the early 1980s, the traditional approach to harmonization through detailed technical directives had proven inadequate. The process of developing detailed technical specifications for each product category was extremely slow—often taking a decade or more—and by the time directives were finally adopted, technology had frequently moved on, rendering the specifications obsolete. The Commission also lacked the technical expertise to develop detailed specifications across the full range of industrial products, and the resulting directives often became entangled in disputes over technical details that had little bearing on actual safety.

On 7 May 1985, the Council adopted the historic Resolution on a new approach to technical harmonization and standards (EUR-Lex 1985). The resolution marked a shift in European product regulation, establishing principles that would govern not only medical devices but virtually all regulated products in the Community. Instead of detailed technical specifications in legislation, directives would define only “essential requirements” for health and safety, expressed in terms of objectives rather than technical solutions. Technical details would be developed through harmonized European standards by CEN (European Committee for Standardization) and CENELEC (European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization).

The New Approach introduced several principles that continue to define European product regulation today. Although designed as a horizontal framework applicable across diverse product sectors—from toys and machinery to construction products and electromagnetic compatibility—these principles proved influential for medical devices. First, compliance with voluntary harmonized standards creates a presumption of conformity with essential requirements—manufacturers who follow European standards are presumed to meet legal requirements, simplifying the compliance process. Second, manufacturers bear primary responsibility for assessing the conformity of their products and applying the CE marking, which certifies compliance with essential requirements. Third, depending on risk level, independent third-party bodies—later formalized as “notified bodies” in implementing directives—may be required to perform conformity assessment, with the extent of their involvement proportionate to the risk

presented by the product. Fourth, Member States are obligated to accept products bearing CE marking from other Member States, eliminating technical barriers to trade.

Directive 84/539/EEC (17 September 1984) represented the first attempt at sectoral harmonization for electro-medical devices, establishing requirements for electrical safety and electromagnetic compatibility based on International Electrotechnical Commission standards (EUR-Lex 1984). While limited in scope, this directive demonstrated the feasibility of applying harmonized technical standards to medical equipment and paved the way for the medical device directives that followed.

The medical device directives

Directive 90/385/EEC (20 June 1990) on active implantable devices marked the beginning of harmonized European medical device regulation. The directive covered pacemakers, cardioverter-defibrillators, insulin pumps, cochlear implants, and other devices that are implanted in the human body and require an electrical or other energy source to function (EUR-Lex 1990). The directive established the architecture that would be replicated in subsequent medical device legislation: essential requirements, classification based on risk, conformity assessment procedures proportionate to risk level, and the notified body system.

Directive 93/42/EEC (14 June 1993) established a framework for most medical devices, creating the regulatory architecture that governed the European market for over two decades (EUR-Lex 1993). The directive introduced four risk classes—Class I (lowest risk), Class IIa (medium risk), Class IIb (elevated risk), and Class III (highest risk)—determined through 18 classification rules that considered factors such as invasiveness, duration of contact with the body, and whether the device was active or passive.

Clinical evaluation requirements were included in Directive 93/42/EEC, requiring manufacturers to demonstrate safety and performance through clinical data. However, these requirements proved more lenient than those applied to pharmaceuticals—a disparity that was severely criticized after subsequent scandals revealed that high-risk implants had reached the market based on limited clinical evidence (Fraser et al. 2011; Hwang et al. 2016). The directive allowed extensive use of equivalence claims, whereby manufacturers could rely on clinical data from similar devices rather than conducting their own clinical investigations.

Directive 98/79/EC (27 October 1998) established the framework for *in vitro* diagnostic devices, addressing the characteristics of laboratory tests and diagnostic equipment (EUR-Lex 1998). Together, these three directives—the Active Implantable Medical Devices Directive, the Medical Devices Directive, and the *In Vitro* Diagnostic Directive—governed the European medical device market for over two decades, creating the regulatory environment that was later reformed by MDR and IVDR.

Regulatory crises as stress tests (2005–2012)

The period from 2005 through 2012 witnessed high-profile medical device failures that challenged the European regulatory system. These crises occurred against the backdrop of reform discussions already underway—the European Commission had initiated evaluation of the existing framework, evolving into a proposal for a regulation (EUR-Lex 2012). During this period, several scandals served as dramatic stress tests, confirming systemic weaknesses and providing compelling evidence for reforms already under consideration.

The Guidant pacemaker scandal

The Guidant crisis of 2005 exposed gaps in post-market surveillance and manufacturer transparency. The company failed to disclose known defects in implantable cardioverter-defibrillators for several years, resulting in patient deaths (Maisel et al. 2006). Internal documents revealed that Guidant had identified a potentially fatal short-circuit problem but continued selling existing inventory rather than issuing immediate recalls.

When the defect became public following a young man's death, it emerged that the company had known about the problem for 3 years while thousands of patients received defective devices. The case demonstrated that voluntary reporting systems were inadequate for protecting public safety and became a catalyst for strengthened coordination between EU and US regulatory authorities.

The DePuy (articular surface replacement) ASR hip prosthesis scandal

The DePuy ASR metal-on-metal hip prosthesis scandal (2003–2010) revealed problems with the equivalence pathway for high-risk implants and illustrated regulatory divergence between Europe and the United States. DePuy's ASR system (Johnson and Johnson) received CE marking based on limited clinical data and claimed equivalence with other metal-on-metal prostheses, despite failure rates far exceeding acceptable norms (Cohen 2011).

The FDA rejected the ASR XL Acetabular System for insufficient clinical data—it never reached the US market—while in Europe both ASR models received CE marking and were implanted in approximately 93,000 patients (Cohen 2012). When failures became apparent, with revision rates reaching 49% at 6 years due to metallosis and adverse tissue reactions, the regulatory divergence became a central argument for strengthening European clinical evidence requirements.

A subsequent *BMJ* investigation revealed that a fictitious device application submitted as a journalistic experiment successfully obtained CE marking from a notified body, demonstrating inadequate scrutiny of clinical data (Cohen 2013). The exposure—that devices rejected by the FDA could receive European approval and that

notified bodies might certify devices without rigorous evaluation—undermined public confidence in the European system.

The PIP scandal: criminal fraud as a systemic stress test

The Poly Implant Prothèse (PIP) scandal of 2010 was a criminal case—the French company systematically used industrial-grade silicone instead of approved medical-grade material in breast implants for approximately a decade, a deliberate fraud affecting around 400,000 women worldwide (Santanelli di Pompeo F et al. 2022). The fraud occurred despite regular inspections by TÜV Rheinland, the German notified body responsible for certification.

While the case represented criminal behavior rather than regulatory design failure, it exposed systemic weaknesses: insufficient frequency and depth of inspections, potential conflicts of interest in the notified body financing model (where bodies are paid by manufacturers they evaluate), lack of coordination between national authorities, and weak post-market surveillance.

Scientific community response

The collective impact of these scandals—affecting hundreds of thousands of patients—confirmed the necessity of reforms already under discussion. *The Lancet* (2012) published an editorial calling for reform, and in January 2012, the European Commission published a Joint Plan for Immediate Actions (European Commission 2012).

The European medical community, particularly cardiologists and orthopedists, provided systematic evidence supporting reform (Fraser et al. 2011). The central argument was that Europe applied double standards—requiring strict clinical evidence for drugs while allowing high-risk implantable devices based on much more limited data. Comparative research documented higher post-market safety alert rates for European-approved versus FDA-approved devices (Hwang et al. 2016). This scientific consensus formed the intellectual foundation for MDR and IVDR.

The regulatory revolution: MDR and IVDR

Legislative process and adoption

The adoption of Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on 5 April 2017 represents the culmination of a legislative process spanning nearly a decade (EUR-Lex 2017a). The reform was officially initiated in 2008, when the European Commission began evaluation of the existing framework, recognizing that technological developments and emerging safety concerns required revision of the 1990s directives. The legislative process was catalyzed by the crises of the late 2000s and early 2010s, especially the PIP scandal, which provided evidence for the necessity of reform.

In January 2012, the Commission published legislative proposals for revision of the medical device framework. Intensive interinstitutional negotiations followed from 2012 to 2016, involving complex discussions on issues such as clinical evidence requirements, notified body oversight, transparency, and transitional provisions. The final text was adopted on 5 April 2017, with impressive parliamentary support—525 votes in favor and only 13 against—reflecting broad consensus across political groups that reform was necessary to restore public confidence in the European medical device system.

Enhanced clinical evaluation

A key change in MDR is the transformed standards for clinical evidence, directly addressing criticism that the directive-era system allowed high-risk devices to reach the market based on inadequate data. For implantable and high-risk devices (Class IIb and Class III), the regulation introduces mandatory clinical studies as the general rule, with exceptions only under clearly defined conditions—proven equivalence with already approved devices or situations in which conducting a clinical study would be unethical or technically impossible.

The concept of equivalence, previously applied liberally and often abused to avoid clinical investigations, is now strictly defined. Under MDR, equivalence requires demonstration of identity in clinical, biological, and technical characteristics—the equivalent device must be the same in terms of clinical purpose, design, materials, and manufacturing process. MDR requires the manufacturer to have a contract with the manufacturer of the equivalent device to access full technical documentation, effectively preventing equivalence claims based on publicly available information about competitor products.

Clinical evaluation under MDR becomes an ongoing process. Requirements include critical evaluation of relevant scientific literature using systematic review methodology, systematic analysis of available clinical data from the device itself and equivalent devices, identification of the need for additional clinical studies where gaps exist, benefit-risk analysis considering all available evidence, and development of detailed post-market clinical follow-up (PMCF) plans for continuous data collection after market placement. These requirements reflect scientific consensus regarding stricter methodologies for clinical evaluation of high-risk devices (Fraser et al. 2025).

Strengthened oversight and expert panels

Notified body oversight changed under MDR. The creation of the Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) as a permanent expert body at the European level is an institutional innovation. The MDCG assumes central roles in coordinating competent authority activities across Member States, developing guidelines for uniform application of MDR requirements, and ensuring

consistency in interpretation and enforcement across the European market.

Notified body designation requirements became more demanding. Notified bodies must demonstrate expertise not only in technical aspects but also in clinical evaluation and specific therapeutic areas. Mandatory unannounced inspections, both of notified bodies and of manufacturers they certify, create mechanisms for continuous quality monitoring. The Commission and Member States obtained enhanced powers to suspend or withdraw notified body designations where deficiencies are identified.

Expert panels create mechanisms for independent scientific expertise in evaluating the highest-risk devices. Established through Article 106 of MDR, these panels consist of leading clinical, scientific, and technical experts nominated by Member States and selected based on their expertise. For Class III high-risk implantable devices and certain Class IIb active devices intended to administer medicines, notified bodies must submit clinical evaluation dossiers for mandatory consultation through the Clinical Evaluation Consultation Procedure (CECP) before issuing certificates (Fraser et al. 2025). This procedure addresses criticism that notified bodies often lacked sufficient clinical expertise to evaluate complex implants and high-risk active devices.

Post-market surveillance and transparency

The post-market surveillance system transforms from a relatively passive incident-reporting mechanism into a proactive system for continuous monitoring of device performance in real-world clinical use. New requirements include detailed surveillance plans for each device, specifying how manufacturers will collect and analyze post-market data. Mandatory Periodic Safety Update Reports (PSURs) for implantable and Class III devices require systematic review and reporting of safety data at regular intervals.

Vigilance requirements are strengthened with shorter reporting deadlines for serious incidents and field safety corrective actions. Post-market clinical follow-up (PMCF) plans become mandatory for high-risk devices, requiring proactive collection of clinical data after market placement to confirm long-term safety and performance that could not be fully established in pre-market investigations.

Transparency improves through EUDAMED—the European Database on Medical Devices. The centralized information management system covers device registration with unique device identifiers (UDIs), enabling traceability from production to patient, economic operator information, notified body certificates and their scope, clinical study registration and results, and vigilance data, including incident reports and field safety actions. The UDI system creates mechanisms for unambiguous identification of every device, enabling recalls to be conducted more efficiently and facilitating post-market surveillance across borders.

Implementation challenges

MDR implementation proved more complex than anticipated, creating challenges that continue to affect the European medical device market. Notified body capacity immediately became critical—many bodies operating under the directives chose not to seek designation under the new regulation due to increased expertise requirements and liability concerns. The number of designated notified bodies dropped from approximately 58 under the directives to fewer than 30 initially designated under MDR, creating severe bottlenecks in certification capacity. By 2024, the number had risen to 46, but capacity remains insufficient for the volume of devices requiring recertification.

Due to systemic capacity shortages and the high risk of critical device shortages that could harm patients, transitional periods for legacy devices have been extended twice. Regulation (EU) 2023/607 provided extended deadlines of 31 December 2027 for Class III and Class IIb implantable devices and 31 December 2028 for remaining risk classes (EUR-Lex 2023). Regulation (EU) 2024/1860 extended these deadlines by another year—to 31 December 2028 and 31 December 2029, respectively (EUR-Lex 2024a). These extensions demonstrate the system's capacity for pragmatic adaptation when faced with implementation crises that could threaten device availability.

Regulation (EU) 2017/746 on *in vitro* diagnostic medical devices (IVDR) represents a parallel reform, with restructured classification from the list-based approach of the old directive to a rule-based system with four risk classes (A–D) (EUR-Lex 2017b). Enhanced requirements for demonstrating both analytical performance and clinical performance, along with mandatory consultation with EU reference laboratories for the highest-risk Class D devices, address challenges related to diagnostic accuracy and clinical utility in laboratory medicine.

Emerging challenges: artificial intelligence in medical devices

The AI Act and medical devices

With the adoption of Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AI Act), published in the Official Journal on 12 July 2024 and entering into force on 1 August 2024, software as a medical device (SaMD) based on artificial intelligence now falls under a dual regulatory framework (EUR-Lex 2024b). It is a notable recent development in European medical device regulation.

According to Article 6(1) of the AI Act, if a product is subject to third-party conformity assessment by a Notified Body under sectoral legislation such as MDR or IVDR, it is automatically classified as a high-risk AI system under the AI Act. This creates a direct legal link between the two regulatory frameworks.

Table 1. Chronological table of key events in European medical device regulation.

Date	Event
25 March 1957	Signing of the Treaty of Rome
1957–1962	Thalidomide tragedy
26 January 1965	Directive 65/65/EEC on medicinal products
17 September 1984	Directive 84/539/EEC on electromedical devices
7 May 1985	Resolution on the New Approach to technical harmonization
1989	Fall of the Berlin Wall; Eastern European transitions begin
20 June 1990	Directive 90/385/EEC on active implantable medical devices
14 June 1993	Directive 93/42/EEC on medical devices
27 October 1998	Directive 98/79/EC on <i>in vitro</i> diagnostic medical devices
2005	Guidant pacemaker scandal
2003–2010	DePuy ASR hip prosthesis scandal unfolds
12 June 2007	Bulgarian Law on Medical Devices enters into force
2008	European Commission initiates comprehensive framework evaluation
2010	PIP breast implant fraud revealed
January 2012	European Commission Joint Plan for Immediate Actions
5 April 2017	Adoption of MDR (2017/745) and IVDR (2017/746)
26 May 2021	MDR enters into application
26 May 2022	IVDR enters into application
12 July 2024	AI Act (2024/1689) published in the Official Journal
1 August 2024	AI Act enters into force

* The *acquis communautaire* (or EU *acquis*) is the entire body of common rights, laws, obligations, and EU policies that bind all European Union Member States, essentially “EU law as it stands.” It includes treaties, legislation (directives and regulations), court rulings, declarations, and international agreements, requiring candidate countries to fully adopt it before joining the EU.

The single conformity assessment principle

To prevent a dual bureaucratic burden that could block innovation, the EU has established an integration mechanism. Article 43(3) of the AI Act explicitly provides that conformity assessment of the AI system must be integrated into existing MDR procedures. As a result, the Notified Body certifying a medical device under MDR will simultaneously verify compliance with AI Act requirements.

This integration has practical implications. Notified bodies must obtain additional accreditation to assess AI aspects of devices. Data governance requirements under the AI Act are substantially stricter than MDR requirements for data quality, training data sets, and algorithmic transparency. The intersection of technological safety requirements with clinical efficacy standards creates challenges for manufacturers and regulators.

Implications for the regulatory framework

The dual framework for AI-based medical devices represents an evolution of the European approach—extending beyond traditional medical device safety to encompass broader considerations of algorithmic accountability, bias prevention, and explainability. Software as a medical device (SaMD) based on artificial intelligence must now demonstrate compliance with both technological safety requirements under the AI Act and clinical performance requirements under MDR, ensuring coherence between technological security and clinical efficacy.

This reflects European regulatory philosophy—the application of the precautionary principle to emerging technologies, combined with recognition that AI in healthcare requires specific safeguards beyond traditional device regulation.

Comparative perspectives: Europe and the United States

The FDA system features centralized authority with standardized procedures and direct accountability (Sorenson and Drummond 2014). The European system distributes responsibilities among 27 national authorities, multiple notified bodies, and the MDCG. The FDA traditionally imposes stricter clinical evidence requirements, especially for high-risk Class III devices requiring premarket approval.

MDR tightened European requirements toward FDA standards, although differences remain. The European system traditionally provided faster market access (6–12 months versus 1–3+ years for premarket approval); MDR has increased certification times to 11–12 months (Gupte et al. 2025). Movement toward convergence continues through international forums such as the International Medical Device Regulators Forum, especially for software- and AI-based devices, where both jurisdictions face similar novel challenges.

Conclusion

The evolution of European medical device regulation over five decades demonstrates adaptability to technological challenges, growing public expectations, and periodic

crises. From the fragmented national approaches of the 1970s, characterized by incompatible requirements that impeded trade while providing inconsistent levels of patient protection, to the 2017 regulations, the European system has changed while maintaining core principles of harmonization and mutual recognition.

The historical analysis reveals several lessons for understanding the current regulatory framework. First, the diverse national models of the pre-harmonization era—British emphasis on post-market surveillance and manufacturer responsibility, French delegated evaluation through accredited laboratories, and German regulation through technical standardization—provided conceptual building blocks that were integrated rather than simply replaced by European harmonization. These national innovations continue to influence contemporary approaches to device oversight.

Second, regulatory reform in the medical device sector has been predominantly reactive, driven by crises rather than proactive risk assessment. The thalidomide tragedy shaped pharmaceutical regulation that indirectly influenced device oversight; later device-specific scandals catalyzed MDR and IVDR. The Guidant, DePuy ASR, and PIP scandals—while differing in nature, from technical failures to deliberate criminal fraud—exposed systemic weaknesses in the directive-era framework, demonstrating the necessity of reforms that had been under consideration since 2008.

Third, the challenges faced by Eastern European countries, including Bulgaria, during their transition from centrally planned economies and subsequent EU accession show that effective regulatory capacity cannot be built overnight. These countries had to simultaneously build institutional infrastructure and transpose complex European legislation without the benefit of decades of gradual development. Continuing capacity constraints in some Member States remain relevant for MDR implementation, where demands on regulatory infrastructure are substantially greater than under the previous directives.

The adoption of the AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) adds a new dimension to medical device regulation, creating a dual framework for AI-based devices that integrates technological safety requirements with clinical efficacy standards. AI in healthcare presents risks requiring specific safeguards beyond traditional device regulation, such as algorithmic bias, training data quality, and explainability.

MDR and IVDR address identified weaknesses through strengthened clinical evidence requirements, enhanced notified body oversight, independent expert panels, post-market surveillance, and transparency through EUDAMED. The

success of the European regulatory system depends on effective implementation by Member States and notified bodies, adequate regulatory capacity that continues to be developed, and continuous adaptation to technological innovation. The challenge remains achieving an optimal balance between stimulating beneficial innovation and protecting public health in an era of rapid technological change in medicine.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

Claude 4.5 Sonnet used for unification and checking references format is compliant to journal requirements, citations quality additionally verified with human oversight.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Iana Simova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3458-3684>

Valentina Petkova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6938-1054>

Sava Ognyanov <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-5134-1445>

Kalina Andreevska <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6709-816X>

Milen Dimitrov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7744-0384>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Bulgarian Law on Medical Devices (2007) Medical Devices Act, promulgated, State Gazette No. 46 of 12 June 2007.
- Cohen D (2011) Out of joint: The story of the ASR. *BMJ* 342: d2905. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d2905>
- Cohen D (2012) How safe are metal-on-metal hip implants? *BMJ* 344: e1410. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.e1410>
- Cohen D (2013) How a fake hip showed up failings in European device regulation. *BMJ* 347: f6405. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.e7090>
- Constituzione Italiana (1948) Constitution of the Italian Republic.
- Daemrlich A (2002) A Tale of Two Experts: Thalidomide and Political Engagement. *Social History of Medicine* 15(1): 137–158. <https://doi.org/10.1093/shm/15.1.137>

- Décret (1978) French ministerial decree establishing homologation procedures for medical devices.
- EUR-Lex (1957) Treaty establishing the European Economic Community. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:11957E>
- EUR-Lex (1965) Council Directive 65/65/EEC of 26 January 1965 on medicinal products. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31965L0065>
- EUR-Lex (1984) Council Directive 84/539/EEC on electromedical equipment. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31984L0539>
- EUR-Lex (1985) Council Resolution on a new approach to technical harmonization (85/C 136/01). [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31985Y0604\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31985Y0604(01))
- EUR-Lex (1990) Council Directive 90/385/EEC on active implantable medical devices. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31990L0385>
- EUR-Lex (1993) Council Directive 93/42/EEC concerning medical devices. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31993L0042>
- EUR-Lex (1998) Directive 98/79/EC on in vitro diagnostic medical devices. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31998L0079>
- EUR-Lex (2005) European Commission Progress Reports on Bulgaria's EU accession preparation. Council Directive 2006/96/EC. Technical adaptations for Bulgaria's accession.
- EUR-Lex (2012) Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on medical devices, and amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52012PC0542>
- EUR-Lex (2017a) Regulation (EU) 2017/745 on medical devices (MDR). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32017R0745>
- EUR-Lex (2017b) Regulation (EU) 2017/746 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices (IVDR). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32017R0746>
- EUR-Lex (2023) Regulation (EU) 2023/607 amending Regulation (EU) 2017/745. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32023R0607>
- EUR-Lex (2024a) Regulation (EU) 2024/1860 amending Regulations 2017/745 and 2017/746. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1860>
- EUR-Lex (2024b) Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (AI Act). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1689>
- European Commission (2012) Joint Plan for Immediate Actions following PIP implants crisis.
- Fraser AG, Daubert J-C, Van de Werf F, Mark Estes III NA, Smith Jr SC, Krucoff MW, Vardas PE, Komajda M, Anker S, Auricchio A, Bailey S, Bonhoeffer P, Borggrefe M, Brodin L-Å, Bruining N, Buser P, Butchart E, Gordo JC, Cleland J, Danchin N, Daubert J, Degertekin M, Demade I, Denjoy N, Derumeaux G, Mario CD, Dickstein K, Dudek D, Estes N, Farb A, Flotats A, Fraser A, Gueret P, Israel C, James S, Kautzner J, Komajda M, Krucoff M, Lombardi M, Marwick T, Mioulet M, O'Kelly S, Perrone-Filardi P, Rosano G, Rosenhek R, Sabate M, Smith S, Swahn E, Tavazzi L, Werf FVd, van der Velde E, van Herwerden L, Vardas P, Voigt J-U, Weaver D, Wilmschurst P (2011) Clinical evaluation of cardiovascular devices: principles, problems, and proposals for European regulatory reform: Report of a policy conference of the European Society of Cardiology. *European Heart Journal* 32(13): 1673–1686. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehr171>
- Fraser AG, Redberg RF and Melvin T (2025) The Origins of Regulations for Pharmaceutical Products and Medical Devices – What Can be Learned for the Governance of Medical Devices in Europe? *European Review* 33(5): 521–554. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1062798725000109>
- Gerätesicherheitsgesetz (1968) German equipment safety law. BGBl. I S. 717.
- Gupte T, Nitave T, Goburru J (2025) Regulatory pathways and approval time for medical devices. *Frontiers in Medical Technology* 7: 1586070. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmedt.2025.1586070>
- Hancher L (1990) *Regulating for competition*. Oxford University Press.
- Hwang TJ, Sokolov E, Franklin JM, Kesselheim AS (2016) Comparison of rates of safety issues and reporting of trial outcomes for medical devices approved in the European Union and United States: cohort study. *BMJ* 353: i3323. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i3323>
- The Lancet (2012) Editorial The scandal of device regulation in Europe. *Lancet* 379(9811): 96. [https://thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(12\)60041-5/fulltext](https://thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(12)60041-5/fulltext)
- Maisel WH, Moynahan M, Zuckerman BD, Gross TP, Tovar OH, Tillman D-B, Schultz DB (2006) Pacemaker and ICD generator malfunctions. *JAMA* 295(16): 1901–1906. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.295.16.1901>
- Medicines Act (1968) UK Public General Acts c. 67. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1968/67>
- MedGV (1985) Medizinische-Geräteverordnung of 14 January 1985. BGBl. I S. 102. 1968/67
- Ministero della Salute (1979) Italian Ministry of Health mandatory registration of medical devices.
- Nordic Council (1975) Nordic Council on Medicines. Regional cooperation framework.
- Rägo L, Santoso B (2008) Drug regulation: history, present and future. In: van Boxtel CJ et al. (Eds) *Drug Benefits and Risks*. IOS Press, 65–77.
- Regio Decreto (1934) Regio Decreto 27 luglio 1934, n. 1265 (Testo Unico delle leggi sanitarie).
- Sampietro-Colom L, Asua J, Briones E, Gol J (2009) History of health technology assessment: Spain. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care* 25(S1): 174–181. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s026646230909059x>
- Santaneli di Pompeo F, Paolini G, Firmani G, Sorotos M (2022) History of breast implants: Back to the future. *JPRAS Open* 32:166–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jprra.2022.02.004>
- Socialstyrelsen (1968) Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare.
- Sorenson C, Drummond M (2014) Improving medical device regulation. *Milbank Quarterly* 92(1): 114–150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0009.12043>